

The Impact of talent management on employee's performance in the Organization

MS. LAVINA CHRISTIAN

Research Scholar,
Department of Management studies,
Sankalchand Patel University,
Visnagar

DR. JITENDRA K.SHARMA

Professor & Dean,
Department of Management studies,
Sankalchand Patel University,
Visnagar

Abstract

Most of the organizations have considered talent management as highly important practice for the development of the organization. At initial period some organizations have taken this function lightly, but now it's a high time for industries. The biggest challenge for any industry is to retain talent for long period of time. Many organizations have developed different talent management practices to enhance the employee performance. Organizations put their maximum efforts in functioning such practices, so that they can get maximum input of employees. Such talent management practices can develop positive relationship between employees and management. This Study has revealed that talent management practices have positive effects on employee's performance.

Keywords: Talent management, Employee performance, Organizational performance, Employee Retention

Introduction

Human resource management has adopted talent management as one of the most important asset of organization development. It helps employees by offering appropriate job which matches to their talent, skill abilities and passion. This can increase organizational performance and productivity level. Talent management is equally important for both employees and organization. Talent management can enhance employee's ability which can definitely increase the productivity.

Definitions

Talent

“Talent is considered as individual’s abilities or inherent skills, knowledge, gifts, intelligence, experience or his/her capability to grasp new thing and grow” (Woodward & Beechler)

Talent Management

- “Talent management is a process of attracting, recruiting, selecting ,developing, promoting, and retaining the talented, skilled, competent employee in the same organization for longer period to achieve the organizational goal.
- “Talent management is the processes of ensuring that talented people are attracted, retained, motivated and developed in line with the needs of the organization”.

-M. Armstrong

- “Talent management involves implementing a set of key activities as part of human resources management, while simultaneously applying more advanced methods and techniques.”

-S. Borkowska

Objective of the study

- To understand concept of Talent Management.
- To understand the various talent management practices applicable in the organizations.
- To study the impact of Talent Management practices on the performance of employees.
- To study the impact of Talent Management practices on the performance of Organization.

Scope of the study

This paper will focus on various talent management practices adopted by organization by reviewing the research papers and articles relevant impact of these practices on the performance of the employees

In early 90s, when Indian economical system have reinforced due to liberalization, privatization and globalization, this huge change has created big opportunities for people to work in banks and industries. Organizations has developed talent management practices which do not stick to recruitment but also believes in ongoing development by attracting , recruiting, advancing, retaining and preparing employees to fulfill organizational goal. For example organization has to provide extraordinary benefit to attract talented employees of competitor companies.

Recruiting talented candidate is not only enough but to get his maximum input to achieve the target is the main motto. That’s why, it’s realized that talent management takes care of employees from starting job till leaving organization. Here every individual wants to win the match for and for that they have to be very competent, dedicated and updated with the outer world.

There are many researchers who had studied about various areas of talent management practices but still it has become very difficult to understand the actual ideal of it. There are some organizations which has adopted different talent management practices with creative ideas.

Some researchers have discussed that to manage the special employee is not a easy task. It consumes lot of time and money though it is useful. Top management put their maximum efforts in valuing and developing their employees but does not give sufficient time and materials (resources) which is essential. **(Heinen & Neil,2004)** Only those organizations get continuous success which believes in progress and development by keeping their talent for the longest time with them. Researcher also discussed that talent management is not administrator work but it is a business strategy which focus more on highly skilled employees.

Talented employees are the valuable asset for to develop organizational performance as well as employee performance. Organization has to recognize the special talent which contributes in achieving organizational vision. If HR fails to keep talent at right place at right time can create solid chaos regardless of having talents, abilities and caliber of the employees.

There was deep interest by discussing the growing possible area of employee's progress and their capability development which was developed as Talent management strategies in the organization. **(Kumari & Bahuguna,2012)** They have observed some conflicts while implementation of talent management strategies.

Study has resulted that effectiveness among employees who were not recognized as talented employee. They have also focused on the some solutions to reduce retention issue such as work life balance, effective compensation, career development and succession planning of employees.

There are three important areas of talent management. Some organizations took talent management as part of HRM wherein some are taking talent management as routine practices of HR, such as recruitment, career development, selection etc. **(Lewis & Heckman, 2006)** Their perspective focuses more on employees needs and third way of perspective focuses on managing talented people.

It is the failure of the talent management practices if management place right candidate at wrong place. Many employers find this TM strategies very inappropriate and unethical because they lose their best talent but in this modern competitive market, entire talent management process sounds very appropriate and ethical because here biggest question was of survival.

The researchers have identified in their study regarding global and financial forces to the people and organizational mobility. The organizational culture and environment has become more challenging demanding and difficult. Employees perceive on career and succession planning and cultural and other transformation can lead to industries. Employees should have higher skills, talents, public relation, new HR strategies, leadership quality and career development plans.

Organizations have developed various diversity in recruitment procedures, working culture, gender, age generations, way of working patterns than past. **(Beechler & Woodward,2009)** This diversity can be useful in problem solving. In spite of such global internal circumstances, industries ability to attract, to recruit, to develop, to inspire and to convince talent to stay for longer time will be in a critical situation in this century.

There is a study on oil and gas industry having large demand of oil and gas which has huge demand for talented people for the work. The main objective was to understand the effects of talent management on employee inspiration, innovation skill development. Data collection was done through multiple regressions method. Employees of this filed were not aware about

the latest technologies. **(Kumari & Bahuguna,2012)** The major problems were facing multiple retirement, attrition and lack of talent. It was found that employee engagement is totally connected with talent management.

Talent management as an important process and practice in business which has differences in talent management practices in reference to employee induction, recruitment, selection, training, career succession, planning and recognition. DIME framework was proposed in which skill, abilities, talent, competencies, employee engagement were discussed completely. Talent management practices focus recruitment till retention and result of their performance, HR practitioners have to know, understand, manage the practices and developmental strategies of talent management practices. **(Robert Silzer & Ben Dowell, 2014)**At the same time, some practice has to be withdrawn if they are not worth. For the successful implementation of talent management practices, the organizer has to understand the current condition system and process of the organization.

The organizations have understood global talent management as procedure of recruitment, selection, training and development, promotion and development to achieve organizational objectives. Many multinational companies have adopted Global Talent Management as the highest requirement of firm. They used the survey method for the data collection in multinational companies. It was found from the study the talent acquisition can play effective role in low retention rate which can increase organizational productivity and creativity. **(Tamzini, Khaled, Ayed,2017)** Multinational companies highly prefer foreign professional managers rather than local ones. They make solutions for the future challenges related to talent management.

There is positive Impact of Talent management practices on employee's performance in private banks of Haryana. Study has total eight segments which affects employee's motivation, employee's satisfaction, employee's creativity, employee's competency level, employee's efficiency and employee's development.**(Hitu & Satyawan Baroda,2018)**salary is not only the factor but nonmonetary benefits, target achievement, enhanced leadership skills, stress free organizational culture, career opportunities are the attracting factors which affects to employee performance.

Impact of Talent Management practices on Employee Performance

In every field, There is a requirement of taking care of human efforts and molding them into organizational culture. Hospitality and medical field also talent management practices have shown positive result in improving employees as well as organizational performance. There was a study on effects of talent management practices on the employee productivity and performance in medical health sector in Pakistan in which quantitative and cross sectional approach for the study convenience sampling method was used for the data collection and has used questionnaire method. The major findings was revealed that there was highly positive impact on the employee’s performance by implementing talent management practices, such as recruiting, selecting, training, mentoring, coaching and compensation management.. **(Munaza Bibi,2018)** It was also suggested that Health Care organizations should definitely develop their strategies to manage specially skilled human resources to retain them for longer period in the same organization.

Talent management practices are equally important as profit of any organization. If any public or private sector industry, bank, institution want to achieve their desire goal then updating of

business strategies and attractive talent management practices have to be effectively implemented. Most of all organizations have initiated the talent management practices at some level, but to stand in competitive market, organizations have to adopt new attractive strategies to attract talent.

Talented employees feel valued, united and important when their skills, abilities and knowledge are taken care of. Talent management emphasis on identifying an individual's skills, abilities, talent, caliber and providing him/her appropriate job. Every individual has extra ordinary talent which suits to a specific job profile.

Organizations ought to give various facilities and acknowledgments to the unique representatives. Organizations should quantify the presentation of skilled representatives and general workers in an unexpected way. Organizations should offer chance to ability to upgrade their aptitudes and capacities and information. Organizations should put the capable workers in appropriate territory where their abilities can be used. Extraordinary worker ought to be given legitimate chance to create which can be used for accomplishing the objectives of the firm.

Findings of the study

- Many organizations have accepted the necessity of change in adopting Talent management practices. Organizational performance can be successfully achieved only when employee's performance is enhanced.
- New technologies, employee's motivation, satisfaction, organizational culture, working environment, compensation, employer and employee relationship these are all factors which needs to be taken care of.
- Most of the Talent management studies have conducted on banks, IT industries and private institutions.
- There can be further studies in academic, hotel industry, NGOs to understand the impact of Talent management practices on these fields too.
- It is revealed that Talent Management practices have huge positive impact on the employee performance.

Conclusion

Organizations become specifically more cautious about the new practices, creative methodologies and formative projects. Organizations change their working patterns as indicated by the market request. Organizations turn out to be progressively precise by actualizing Talent Management. Organizations get incapacitated in the event that the ability leaves each now and, at that point. Organization ought to distinguish the gifted and skilled representatives from the whole workforce .

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